

The Formation and Stability of Polybromide Derivatives of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part II. The Polybromide Ion Derivatives of Alkylaminobenzthiazoles obtained from *s*-Phenylalkylthiocarbamides and Bromine, and a Comparison of the Ease of Nuclear Substitution by Bromine in 1-Alkylaminobenzthiazolium and 1-Imino-2-alkyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazolium Ions.

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In view of the development of our knowledge of the chemistry of polybromide derivatives of heterocyclic compounds of the thiazole type in recent years, it appeared desirable to re-examine some of the earlier experiments on the bromination of *s*-phenylalkylthiocarbamides in chloroform.

The interaction of *s*-phenylalkylthiocarbamides with bromine was first examined some years ago in an investigation having for its main object the study of the relation between tautomeric mobility and unsaturation in semi-cyclic symmetrical triad systems (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1385, 2951). It was observed that certain phenylalkylthiocarbamides gave rise to what appeared to be dibromides and tetrabromides of the corresponding alkylaminobenzthiazoles, to which the formulæ (I) and (II) were assigned.

(I)

(II)

Owing to an erroneous theory of the mechanism of the reaction (Hunter and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2958), it was at this time assumed that bromo-addition compounds of 1-aminobenzthiazoles containing an even number of bromine atoms labile towards sulphurous acid, obtained from arylthiocarbamides, were *true* bromides

(*cf.* Hegershoff, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 3121) of the type of 1-phenylbenzthiazole tetrabromide (Bogert and Abrahamson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 826; Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 537). The possibility that such compounds might be hydroperbromides was unfortunately never entertained, mainly on account of the fact that their formulation on such a basis, would have necessitated the assumption of "odd valency" structures. Later investigations, however, have shown that the bromo-addition compounds obtained by thiazole cyclisation of arylthiocarbamides are invariably *hydroperbromides* (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 125; Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 147), produced by the interaction of the hydrobromides of the thiazole bases initially formed and bromine. It has furthermore been shown that the nuclear nitrogen atom of the benzthiazole complex is the *centre* of unsaturation of the molecule, and that the sulphur atom of the heterocyclic ring resembles that of thiophen in its inertness towards ordinary reagents; due presumably to the fact that its labile electrons are called upon to complete the sextuple group on which the aromatic character of such heterocyclic systems may be assumed to depend (Armit and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127**, 1674, Goss and Ingold, *ibid.*, 1928, 1268; Hunter, *loc. cit.*). Formulae of the type (I) and (II) are therefore clearly erroneous, and since the technique in handling unstable bromo-addition compounds has been considerably improved in recent years the bromination of a number of *s*-phenylalkylthiocarbamides has been carefully re-investigated.

Treatment of a solution of *s*-phenylethylthiocarbamide in chloroform with excess of bromine gave rise to a well-defined *hydro-tetrabromide* of 1-ethylaminobenzthiazole, which was also prepared from the *hydrobromide* of the ethylaminobenzthiazole and bromine (*cf.* Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 134). This compound probably

has the constitution (III), containing a Br_4^\ominus ion, whose production involves the operation of a lone singlet linkage (*cf.* Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *loc. cit.*; Hunter, *Chem. Ind.*, 1932, 939).

(III)

(IV)

Bromination of *s*-phenyl-*n*-propylthiocarbamide in the presence of excess of the halogen, however, yielded an unstable *hydropentabromide* of 1-*n*-propylaminobenzthiazole to which the formula (IV) is assigned on the grounds of analogy with Roozeboom's ammonium pentabromide (*Ber.*, 1881, 14, 2398), which readily lost bromine giving a more stable *hydrotribromide* of the propylaminobenzthiazole. This was also obtained by carrying out the reaction in the presence of a lower concentration of the halogen, and it therefore appears probable that the "tetrabromide" of 1-*n*-propylaminobenzthiazole, isolated under somewhat indefinite conditions in the earlier investigation (*loc. cit.*), consisted of a partially decomposed specimen of the *hydropentabromide* of the base.

Attempts to prepare bromo-addition compounds of 1-*isobutyl*-aminobenzthiazole and 1-*isoamyl*aminobenzthiazole of a higher order than *hydrotribromides* proved unsuccessful; the products of bromination of *s*-phenyl*isobutyl*thiocarbamide and *s*-phenyl*isoamyl*thiocarbamide being tenacious gums which crystallised with difficulty on being kept in *vacuo* over potassium hydroxide, giving the *hydrotribromides* of the corresponding alkylaminobenzthiazoles described in the earlier investigation.

s-Phenyl-*n*-hexylthiocarbamide, however, behaved similarly to the propylthiocarbamide and gave rise to an unstable *hydropentabromide* of 1-*n*-hexylaminobenzthiazole, which lost bromine on exposure to air or on keeping in a desiccator over potassium hydroxide.

A very definite contrast between the properties of the *hydroperbromides* of the 1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles and those derived from 1-imino-2-alkyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazoles (V) is provided by the respective tendencies of the compounds towards nuclear substitution. Thus, the *hydroperbromides* of the alkylaminobenzthiazoles undergo appreciable nuclear substitution by bromine under the ordinary conditions of iodometric titration of labile bromine in chloroform, whereas the bromo-addition compounds of iminoalkyldihydrobenzthiazoles give quantitative values for labile bromine (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 139). Furthermore, the bromo-addition compounds of the alkylaminobenzthiazole series, such as the *hydrotetrabromide* of 1-ethylaminobenzthiazole, undergo nuclear substitution on being boiled in aqueous alcoholic solution, whilst the *hydroperbromides* of iminoalkyldihydrobenzthiazoles, in so far as they have been studied,

merely yield hydrobromides of the unsubstituted dihydrobenzthiazole bases under such conditions (*loc. cit.*).

This difference in behaviour towards hydroxylic solvents is evidently attributable to the higher reactivity of the *para* position to the ring nitrogen atom in the thiazolium ion of the aromatic heterocyclic base towards bromine or hypobromous acid formed by decomposition of the polybromide complex in aqueous hydroxylic solvents.

The 1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles behave similarly to the iminoalkyl-dihydrobenzthiazoles on bromination in chloroform, and undergo nuclear substitution with the production of hydroperbromides of the corresponding 5-bromo-1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles. Thus, the isobutylamino base on treatment with excess of bromine, yields a *hydro-pentabromide* (VI) whose constitution follows from its reduction by sulphurous acid to 5-bromo-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole, identical with that obtained from the thiazole cyclisation of *s-p*-bromophenyl-isobutylthiocarbamide (Hunter and Soyka, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

s-Phenylethylthiocarbamide was prepared by treating a solution of phenylthiocarbimide in absolute alcohol with a 20 to 30 % excess of a 33 % solution of ethylamine in water, and had m.p. 99–100° after recrystallisation (Weith, *Ber.*, 1875, 8, 1524).

1-Ethylaminobenzthiazole *hydrotetrabromide* (III). (i) *Bromination of s-phenylethylthiocarbamide*.—Bromine (1 c.c. in 2 c.c. of chloroform) was added to a solution of *s*-phenylethylthiocarbamide in chloroform (1 g. in 7 c.c.) in a Geissler flask, and the mixture was heated on a steam bath under reflux for 2 to 3 minutes and thereafter cooled in ice. The *hydrotetrabromide* crystallised in glistening orange-red needles which were collected on porous earthenware and dried in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide, anhydrous

calcium chloride, and paraffin wax for 5 to 10 minutes. After being crushed on fresh porous tile and again dried in a vacuum for a further 5 minutes, the crystals had m.p. 80–82° (softening and sintering at 70–74°). [Found: Br (total), 64·55; Br (labile), 43·3. $C_9H_{10}N_2S, HBr(Br_3)$ requires Br (total), 64·15; Br (labile), 48·1 per cent]. The hydrotetrabromide dissolved in sulphurous acid giving a colourless solution which yielded 1-ethylaminobenzthiazole on basification with ammonia, which had m.p. 93–94° after recrystallisation from alcohol and drying in a vacuum (previously recorded as m.p. 87–88°).

(ii) *Synthesis from 1-ethylaminobenzthiazole hydrobromide and bromine.*—The hydrobromide of 1-ethylaminobenzthiazole, obtained by treating a hot solution of the ethylamino base (1·5 g.) in absolute alcohol (9 c.c.) with 66 per cent hydrobromic acid (2 c.c.) and allowing the resulting solution to cool, crystallised in soft flakes consisting of small needles, m.p. 219–20°. (Found: Br, 30·7. $C_9H_{10}N_2S, HBr$ requires Br, 30·9 per cent). A warm suspension of this salt (1 g.) in chloroform (8 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0·8 c.c. in 1 c.c. of the same solvent), and the resulting clear red solution was cooled in the ice when the hydrotetrabromide separated in glistening orange red plates, m.p. 90°. [Found: Br (total), 64·0; Br (labile), 42·6 per cent].

Decomposition of 1-ethylaminobenzthiazole hydrotetrabromide by alcohol and the Isolation of 5-Bromo-1-ethylaminobenzthiazole.—A solution of the bromo-addition compound in alcohol was boiled, diluted with water and concentrated on a water-bath when acetaldehyde was evolved. The hydrobromide obtained in this way formed white flaky crystals which had m.p. 240–42° (sintering at 237–40°). It was decomposed with ammonia and the product was crystallised from alcohol when impure 5-bromo-1-ethylaminobenzthiazole was obtained which had m.p. 140°, and m.p. 146–48° when mixed with an authentic specimen prepared from *s-p*-bromophenyl-ethylthiocarbamide.

1-n-Propylaminobenzthiazole hydropentabromide (IV).—A solution of *s*-phenyl-*n*-propylthiocarbamide (Hecht, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 286) (0·7 g.) in chloroform (4 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0·9 c.c. in 0·9 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated on a water-bath under reflux for 2 minutes, and the solution was transferred to a dry crystallising basin and concentrated in a vacuum. The hydropentabromide crystallised in small vermilion crystals which were

collected on porous earthenware, dried in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide, anhydrous calcium chloride and paraffin wax for 2 minutes, transferred to fresh porous earthenware and again dried in a vacuum for a period of 5 to 10 minutes. This compound was highly unstable and showed signs of decomposition into the yellow-orange hydrotribromide on being exposed to moist air for a few minutes. It had m.p. 57-59° (clear red liquid at 60°). [Found: Br (total), 66.3; Br (labile), 52.6. $C_{10}H_{12}N_2S$, HBr (Br_4) requires Br (total), 67.6; Br (labile), 54.1 per cent]. On keeping in a desiccator over potassium hydroxide for 24 hours, it lost bromine yielding the yellow-orange hydrotribromide, and on reduction with sulphurous acid it gave 1-*n*-propylaminobenzthiazole, m.p. 68° (Hunter, *loc. cit.*).

1-n-Propylaminobenzthiazole hydrotribromide.—A solution of the phenylpropylthiocarbamide (1 g.) in chloroform (8 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of the same solvent) and the mixture was heated for 2 minutes and thereafter concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. The yellow-orange crystals obtained in this way had m.p. 57° after being crushed on porous earthenware and dried in a vacuum. [Found: Br (total), 55.6; Br (labile), 36.4. $C_{10}H_{12}N_2S$, HBr (Br_2) requires Br (total), 55.4; Br (labile), 36.6 per cent].

1-isoButylaminobenzthiazole hydrotribromide.—A solution of *s*-phenylisobutylthiocarbamide (Hecht, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 813), in chloroform (1 g. in 12 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.8 c.c. in 0.8 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated and thereafter concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature, when a viscous liquid was obtained which crystallised on keeping. The *hydrotribromide* formed orange crystals, m.p. 98°. [Found: Br (total), 53.1; Br (labile), 33.1. Calc.: Br (total), 53.7; Br (labile), 35.8 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid it gave 1-*iso*-butylaminobenzthiazole which separated from alcohol in glistening needles, m.p. 104°.

5-Bromo-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole hydropentabromide (VI).—A solution of 1-*isobutylaminobenzthiazole* in chloroform (0.5 g. in 6 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.4 c.c. in 0.4 c.c. of chloroform) and the solution was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 5 minutes and thereafter concentrated in a vacuum. The hydropentabromide then crystallised in the form of deep orange-red crystals, m.p. 76-77°. [Found: Br (total), 70.0; Br (labile), 45.0. $C_{11}H_{13}N_2BrS$, HBr (Br_4) requires Br (total), 70.0; Br (labile), 46.0 per cent]. On

reduction with sulphurous acid and basification with ammonia, it yielded 5-bromo-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole which was identified by m.p. and mixed m.p. determinations with an authentic specimen prepared from *s-p*-bromophenylisobutylthiocarbamide (Hunter and Soyka, *loc. cit.*).

1-isoAmylaminobenzthiazole hydrotribromide.—Considerable difficulty was experienced in connexion with the bromination of *s*-phenyl-*iso*amylthiocarbamide in the earlier investigation, and the hydrotribromide of 1-*iso*amylaminobenzthiazole was analysed in the form of a resin (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2956). On this occasion, however, the red gum obtained from the bromination of *s*-phenyl-*iso*amylthiocarbamide under similar conditions to those used in the case of the *isobutyl* derivative, crystallised after keeping in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide for 2 days. The hydrotribromide obtained in this way had m.p. 61-62°. [Found: Br (total), 53.2; Br (labile), 33.0. Calc.: Br (total), 52.3; Br (labile), 34.4 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid it yielded 1-*iso*amylaminobenzthiazole.

s-Phenyl-n-hexylthiocarbamide, prepared from the condensation of phenylthiocarbimide with excess of *n*-hexylamine in alcohol, crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 110° (previously recorded as 103-104°).

1-n-Hexylaminobenzthiazole hydropentabromide.—A solution of the phenylhexylthiocarbamide in chloroform (1.5 g. in 18 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1.2 c.c.) and the solution was heated and thereafter concentrated in a vacuum, when a hydropentabromide separated in red crystals which had m.p. 66-67° after being dried in the usual way. [Found: Br (total), 64.2; Br (labile), 48.8. $C_{13}H_{18}N_2S$, HBr (Br₄) requires Br (total), 62.9; Br (labile), 50.3 per cent]. This compound was highly unstable and rapidly lost bromine on exposure to moist air or on keeping in a desiccator over potassium hydroxide. On reduction with sulphurous acid, it yielded 1-*n*-hexylaminobenzthiazole which had m.p. 67-68° after recrystallisation (previously recorded as 57°).

s-Phenyl-n-heptylthiocarbamide, prepared from phenylthiocarbimide and *n*-heptylamine, had m.p. 78° after recrystallisation (previously recorded as 70-71°). Unfortunately, the quantity of this compound available after purification was small (0.3 g.) and we were unable to make more than a preliminary examination of its bromination in the presence of excess of halogen. Under conditions similar to those employed in the case of the hexylthiocarbamide, it

gave rise to an indefinite orange bromo-addition compound, m.p. 73-74°. [Found: Br, 59·7. $C_{14}H_{20}N_2S$, HBr (Br_3) requires Br, 56·2 and $C_{14}H_{20}N_2S$, HBr (Br_4) requires Br, 61·6 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid, it yielded 1-*n*-heptylaminobenzthiazole which had m.p. 61-62° after recrystallisation (previously recorded as 55°).

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